

Novel indicators to quantify the effectiveness of phase change materials in buildings

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Abstract

The actual effectiveness of phase change materials (PCMs) in achieving building energy savings strongly depends on the number of entire phase change cycles they undergo within a year. While advanced building performance simulation tools are available, evaluating and enhancing the annual effectiveness of PCMs can be challenging. This research aims to address this issue by introducing novel effectiveness indicators that provide a better understanding of the physical behavior of passive PCMs in buildings, thereby enhancing their thermal performance. The proposed indicators quantify the effectiveness of PCMs by comparing the PCM-driven annual energy savings with the PCM heat latent storage capacity installed in the building. A sensitivity analysis is conducted using the Morris method to assess the influence of design variables related to both the building and the PCMs on the new PCM effectiveness indicators. For this, a case study building in Zone 4A (Mixed), according to the ASHRAE 169-2021 climate classification, is employed, and building energy simulations are performed using the EnergyPlus software to evaluate the performance of the different designs. The results reveal that building design variables, such as the window-to-wall ratio, have a significantly higher impact on the effectiveness of PCMs than typically employed PCM design variables, such as melting temperatures. These unprecedented findings indicate that designers could significantly improve the performance of passive PCMs in buildings by simultaneously designing the PCMs along with other building design variables, preferably at the initial stages. Moreover, the results show that a contradiction can exist between the building’s energy performance and the effectiveness of PCMs. This means that buildings with low energy performance achieve the best effectiveness for PCMs.

Keywords: Phase change material, Effectiveness indicators, Energy-efficient building, Heat energy storage, Heating loads, Cooling loads.

1. Introduction

Given the fact that the current building stock is responsible for more than one-third of global energy consumption and nearly 30% of total energy sector emissions [1], decarbonizing this sector has become crucial for achieving the climate goals outlined in the Paris Agreement [2]. This agreement aims to limit global warming to well below 1.5–2 degrees Celsius compared to pre-industrial levels. Considering this, the

development of innovative technologies that reduce energy consumption in buildings while ensuring occupants' indoor comfort becomes highly relevant in addressing climate change and mitigating the impacts of related extreme weather events [3, 4].

Among the existing technologies for improving building energy efficiency, phase change materials (PCMs) have gained attention due to their ability to store and release substantial amounts of heat during their phase transition. By harnessing this physical phenomenon, PCMs can be incorporated into building components to reduce cooling [5, 6] and heating [7, 8] loads, stabilize indoor temperatures [11], and enhance the overall energy performance of buildings [9].

PCMs undergo phase transitions within a narrow temperature range, wherein their specific thermal capacity varies, as shown in Fig. 1. The temperature at which PCMs reach their maximum thermal capacity is known as the melting temperature.

Fig. 1: Scheme of the variable specific thermal capacity of PCMs as a temperature function.

While PCMs have significant energy-saving potential in buildings, their successful implementation is not guaranteed by default. The performance of PCMs strongly relies on the interplay of daily thermal cycles. Without proper design considerations for specific applications, PCMs may not deliver the expected benefits or, in some cases, may even cause undesirable thermal effects. To ensure the successful performance of passive PCMs in buildings, careful attention must be given to the design of their thermophysical properties, quantities, and locations [10]. These factors play a crucial role in optimizing the utilization of PCMs and maximizing their effectiveness in achieving energy and thermal goals in buildings.

Two main approaches are commonly employed to assess the performance of PCMs in buildings. The first approach is based on experimental testing or field monitoring, where physical mock-ups or full-scale buildings are constructed with PCM integrated to collect real-world data [11, 12]. While this approach provides reliable results, it can be costly and presents limitations in evaluating PCM performance under long-term and representative climate conditions, as well as testing different PCM designs under the same conditions.

The second approach is based on building performance simulations [13–15]. In this approach, the building incorporating PCMs is modeled to predict the physical behavior of PCMs and their effects on indoor temper-

atures, energy consumption, and other performance metrics. Building performance simulations allow for the evaluation of different PCM designs under representative climate conditions and long-term periods. It is recommended to use whole building performance simulation software [16] instead of building component-based approaches to accurately represent the integrated performance of the building and the interaction of PCMs with other building physical phenomena. Moreover, building performance simulations can be employed to conduct sensitivity analysis [17] and optimization [18] of PCMs in buildings.

Regarding the design of PCMs in buildings, criteria must be employed to analyze and compare the performance of the different alternatives qualitatively and quantitatively. In this context, several authors [19–21] measure the performance of PCMs using simplified approaches, such as maximum temperature reduction and the time lag between maximum indoor and outdoor temperatures. However, these estimations are certainly not representative of the benefits of PCMs in buildings over long-term periods.

Another common criterion for measuring the performance of PCM on buildings is by using building performance indicators, such as energy consumption and thermal comfort. Saffari et al. [22] utilized the annual total energy consumption as the objective function to design and optimize the PCM melting temperature in a multi-family building under various climate conditions based on the Köppen-Geiger classification. Cascone et al. [15] considered energy consumption and global costs to optimize the thickness and thermophysical properties of two different PCM layers in the external walls of office buildings in Mediterranean climates. Wang et al. [23] conducted a parametric analysis to assess the air conditioning energy demand and room comfort improvement, aiming to identify the optimal selections of PCM wallboards in terms of melting temperature, locations, and thickness in a high-rise office building located in Shanghai, China.

When the performance metrics for PCMs are quantified over long-term periods using representative climatic conditions and integrated methods such as whole building performance simulation software and experimental buildings, these approaches are valid as they measure the performance of PCMs based on the ultimate objectives for which they are designed. However, quantifying the real effectiveness of PCMs can be challenging, even when employing optimization techniques and building performance simulations. For instance, different PCM designs may have the same impact on building performance indicators, such as energy savings, but they may require significantly different amounts of PCM to achieve this. This issue is commonly encountered in PCM design due to the low thermal conductivity of PCMs [24–26]. Consequently, increasing the amount of PCM may enhance the latent storage capacity, but a substantial portion of the PCM might remain unutilized, significantly reducing its effectiveness. Therefore, in the context of PCM applications in buildings, the term “effectiveness” slightly differs from “performance”, since the quantity of PCM employed plays a crucial role in achieving desired results.

Despite the abundance of research available in the literature on PCMs, only a limited number of attempts have been made to propose indicators for measuring their effectiveness in buildings [27–29]. Sun et al. [28] introduced an energy and mass efficiency indicator to evaluate the performance of PCM boards in office buildings across different climatic regions in China for cooling purposes. This indicator considered three factors: the utilization of natural cold energy, the utilization of the PCM board, and the usage of stored cold energy. While this approach is interesting, its applicability is restricted to cooling applications, and it focuses

solely on PCM-related aspects without incorporating the overall building performance.

Bhamare et al. [29] proposed a unique index, the Measure of Key Response (MKR) index, for selecting the optimum phase change material to enhance the thermal performance of building envelopes. This index allows for a comparative evaluation between a PCM-integrated roof and a non-PCM roof based on parameters such as time lag, decrement factor, and total heat gain from the roof surface. The approach proposed by these authors is important as it compares the relative performance between scenarios with and without PCM. However, it lacks a relative evaluation regarding the amount of PCM required to achieve the relative improvement.

Overall, the approaches discussed in the previous references also have limitations because they are designed and validated using a building component approach (e.g., focusing on the building roof alone) rather than considering the entire building. Therefore, there is a need for comprehensive indicators that encompass the overall building performance when evaluating the effectiveness of PCMs in buildings.

In the study by Evola et al. [27], an important contribution was made towards quantifying the performance of PCMs by considering the entire building. They proposed two indicators and a methodology to investigate the effectiveness of PCM wallboards in improving summer thermal comfort in buildings. These indicators were specifically designed to evaluate the completeness of the PCM phase change cycles, which is crucial for their performance in buildings.

The first indicator, called the Frequency of Activation, quantifies the percentage of time during a given period when PCMs undergo a phase change, indicating their activation. However, it should be noted that this indicator provides more qualitative than quantitative information, as the percentage of time PCMs are undergoing phase transition does not necessarily guarantee energy savings or improved thermal comfort. A key factor to consider is the variation in the thermal capacity of PCMs during the phase transition, as shown in Figure 1. The specific heat capacity of PCMs is significantly higher near the peak phase change temperature compared to the phase change onset temperature. As a result, the storage capacity of the PCM can vary considerably based on temperature, even when it is activated.

The second proposed indicator, named PCM storage efficiency, evaluates the daily effective degree of utilization of the latent storage capacity of PCMs. It is defined as the ratio between the actual thermal energy stored by the PCM and its maximum storage capacity. While this indicator offers a valuable physics-based interpretation of PCM behavior, it has some limitations. One drawback is that the amount of heat stored in PCMs daily does not necessarily indicate improvements in the final objectives, such as energy consumption reduction or enhanced occupant thermal comfort. For instance, when PCMs are located on the exterior of the wall, a complete daily cycle of heat charge and discharge can occur without generating positive impacts on the indoor environment. Additionally, this indicator is primarily applicable to cooling applications of PCMs (e.g., summer seasons) and does not consider heating or overall performance (heating + cooling). Moreover, the complexity of computation and implementation of this indicator should be improved.

Other research efforts have been made in this field [30, 31], but they have primarily focused on proposing specific cases or validating indicators previously introduced by other authors.

Based on the literature reviewed, a significant gap remains in the development of general indicators for

quantifying the effectiveness of PCMs in buildings. Therefore, the present contribution aims to redefine the concept of PCM effectiveness in buildings and propose novel indicators to quantify it for various PCM applications. The novelty of these new indicators lies in their basis on the building performance resulting from the incorporation of PCMs. This approach addresses the limitations of previous indicators that solely rely on monitoring the phase change or stored heat in PCMs. Additionally, the proposed approach generalizes the concept of PCM effectiveness, allowing its use in and analysis of different PCM applications in buildings, including heating, cooling, and total performance (i.e., heating and cooling). By employing this innovative approach, the annual effectiveness of PCMs can be predicted, providing a more representative evaluation of PCM performance in real-world building applications. Moreover, these indicators offer a simpler calculation and implementation compared to previous approaches. They can be utilized with data obtained from both building performance simulations and experiments.

2. Methodology

2.1. PCM effectiveness indicator

In the hypothetical case of ideal PCM performance (e.g., daily complete phase change cycles), an amount of PCM capable of storing the maximum peak load (heating or cooling) would be sufficient to reduce the annual total loads of the building to zero. However, achieving such ideal performance is challenging in actual applications of passive PCMs in buildings due to various aspects and limitations related to PCM features and the thermal performance of buildings, such as the significant variations in indoor temperature throughout the year and different climate seasons.

In this context, the use of indicators to quantify the effectiveness of PCMs becomes crucial in assessing their behavior in buildings and developing new methods for designing and researching PCMs to maximize their benefits. As mentioned earlier, an effective indicator for PCMs in buildings should consider not only the physical behavior of PCMs (e.g., PCM temperatures) but also the relative impact on building performance (e.g., thermal comfort and energy consumption) resulting from the incorporation of PCMs. Furthermore, it should account for the thermal latent capacity required to achieve such an impact. Additionally, the ideal indicator should apply to different PCM applications in buildings (i.e., heating, cooling, and total loads) and be able to be estimated using data obtained from both building performance simulations and experiments.

To accomplish the requirements just pointed out, the PCM effectiveness indicator (PCMEI) is proposed as:

$$\text{PCMEI} = \frac{\text{ALS}}{\text{LSC}}, \quad (1)$$

where ALS is the annual load saved (kJ) by the incorporation of PCMs into the building, and LSC is the latent heat storage capacity (kJ) installed in the building using PCMs.

The PCMEI can be calculated for the total loads ($\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Total}}$), heating loads ($\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Heating}}$), and cooling loads ($\text{PCMEI}_{\text{Cooling}}$). Because the performances of PCMs for heating and cooling applications usually have a contradictory nature, it is recommended to calculate and analyze both separately.

The annual loads saved by the incorporation of PCMs into the building (ALS) are calculated as:

$$ALS = AL_{\text{Baseline}} - AL_{\text{PCM}}, \quad (2)$$

where AL_{PCM} are the annual loads (kJ) obtained as a simulation or experimental result for the building design that incorporates PCMs, and AL_{Baseline} are the annual loads (kJ) for the same building design but without PCMs. Through this approach, it is possible to analyze the impact of variations in other building features or passive strategies on the effectiveness of PCMs.

The latent heat storage capacity LSC installed in the building using PCMs is calculated as:

$$LSC = \sum_{i=1}^N m_{\text{PCM}_i} \Delta h_{\text{PCM}_i}, \quad (3)$$

where m_{PCM_i} is the mass (kg) of the PCM_i , and Δh_{PCM_i} is the specific latent heat storage capacity (kJ/kg) of the PCM_i .

Interpretation of PCMEI values. As formulated, the PCM Effectiveness Indicators (PCMEIs) indicate the ratio of saved loads to the installed thermal latent capacity in the buildings. The PCMEIs have a maximum theoretical value of 365, which indicates an optimal performance where the saved loads fully utilize the installed PCM capacity throughout the year. Because the incorporation of PCMs aims to enhance building performance, positive PCMEI values are mostly expected. However, negative PCMEI values may occur if the presence of PCMs leads to a deterioration in building performance. PCMEIs can also be zero if the inclusion of PCMs does not significantly impact the overall building's performance.

2.2. Application of the PCM effectiveness indicators

This section presents a demonstrative example to display the utilization of PCM effectiveness indicators. The case study aims to illustrate the implementation details and investigate the design parameters that have the most significant impact on improving the effectiveness of PCMs. This investigation is performed through a sensitivity analysis, which examines the influence of both the PCMs' and the building's design variables on the effectiveness of PCMs.

2.2.1. Case study building

A rectangular single zone (8 m wide x 6 m long x 2.7 m high) with no interior partitions and a window on the south exposure is employed to evaluate the thermal performance of the different design variable configurations in the sensitivity analysis; see Fig. 2.

The building energy model is implemented in the software EnergyPlus [32] - version 9. A power of 200 W (60% radiative, and 40% convective) is set as the internal load, and a highly insulated slab is employed to minimize the thermal coupling between the ground and indoors. The construction characteristics of the walls for the Baseline model are detailed in Table 1.

To have both heating and cooling loads in the analysis, the building is assumed to be in Osijek (Croatia), which was selected in our previous work [18] as a representative location for the region 4A (Mixed) [33]

Fig. 2: Geometry of the building case study, and the configuration of the roof and walls for the Baseline and PCM models.

Table 1: Wall characteristics of the building case study.

Element	k [W/(m·K)]	Thickness [m]	U [W/(K·m ²)]	R [(K·m ²)/W]	Density [kg/m ³]	c_p (sensible) [J/(kg·K)]
Int. Surface Coeff.			8.290	0.121		
Foam Insulation	0.04	<i>variable</i>	0.651	1.537	10	1400
Wood Siding	0.14	0.0090	15.556	0.064	530	900
Ext. Surface Coeff.			29.300	0.034		
Overall, air-to-air			0.512	1.952		

according to ASHRAE 169-2020 [34]. The cooling degree-day base 10 °C (CDD10) and the heating degree-day base 18 °C (HDD18) for Osijek are 1964°C and 2502°C, respectively. Table 2 summarizes the main monthly meteorological data in Osijek, Croatia.

An ideal HVAC system is used to evaluate the energy performance of the building, whose thermostat control is set to 20 °C for heating and 27 °C for cooling. Therefore, the heating, cooling, and total annual loads of each design analyzed are calculated for the recent typical meteorological year (TMYx.2004-2018) in Osijek, which is obtained from [35].

Table 2: Summary of main meteorological information in Osijek, Croatia.

Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Daily Avg Dry-bulb Temperature [°C]	0.7	3.4	7.6	13.2	17.4	21.8	23.8	22.3	19.0	13.1	7.7	1.4
Daily Range Temperature [°C]	6.0	8.1	9.8	12.2	11.8	11.0	11.5	12.0	12.6	11.1	8.2	6.6
Daily Avg Relative Humidity [%]	89	82	72	69	69	67	69	70	70	80	81	90
Global Horizontal Solar Radiation [kWh/m ²]	1346	2188	3751	5435	6749	7098	6992	6109	4681	2817	1736	1107

2.2.2. Implementation of the sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis of design variables allows for determining which of them have a considerable influence on the different objectives to be studied or optimized [36]. This can be employed to understand the relationship between the inputs and outputs of a system, as well as to screen the less influential design variables. This work selects and implements the Morris method for the sensitivity analysis [37] because of its low computational cost [38]. This method is performed using the Sensitivity Analysis Library (SALib) [39, 40], which is a Python implementation of commonly used sensitivity analysis methods.

A set of design variables is proposed and parameterized in the EnergyPlus model to study their influence on the PCM effectiveness indicators. Two different PCM layers are added on the inside of the roof (PCM2) and walls (PCM1) of the PCM model; see Fig. 2. Therefore, the first four design variables are the PCM thicknesses (THK_{PCM1} and THK_{PCM2}), and the melting temperatures (peak) of PCMs ($\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM1}}}$ and $\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM2}}}$). In addition, some design variables related to the envelope of the building are incorporated to investigate their impact on the proposed PCM effectiveness indicators. These variables are the insulation thickness ($\text{THK}_{\text{INSUL}}$) of the walls, the area window-to-wall ratio (WWR), and the external shading length normalized as the ratio to the window height (ESR).

Therefore, seven design variables ($k = 7$) are analyzed, and four levels are allowed for each one within their domain ranges, as shown in Table 3. The use of $k + 1$ points in the domain space of input variables in different r trajectories of the elementary effects is recommended by Morris [37], which determines the size of the sample as $r(k + 1)$. Thus, 400 samples are obtained for the building with PCMs by employing 50 trajectories ($r = 50$). The corresponding Baseline models and their thermal performances for each of these 400 designs are obtained by removing the PCMs, i.e., employing the same configuration for the I-THK, WWR, and ESR but without PCMs.

Table 3: Building and PCM design variables were employed in the sensitivity analysis.

#	Design variable	ID	Unity	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4
1	Thickness of PCM1 (walls)	THK_{PCM1}	m	0.005	0.020	0.035	0.050
2	Thickness of PCM2 (roof)	THK_{PCM2}	m	0.005	0.020	0.035	0.050
3	Peak melting temperature of PCM1 (walls)	$\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM1}}}$	°C	20.5	22.5	24.5	26.5
4	Peak melting temperature of PCM2 (roof)	$\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM2}}}$	°C	20.5	22.5	24.5	26.5
5	Thickness of insulation in the walls	$\text{THK}_{\text{INSUL}}$	m	0.050	0.083	0.117	0.150
6	Window-to-wall ratio	WWR	%	30	50	70	90
7	External shading ratio (shading length/height of window)	ESR	%	1	34	67	100

2.2.3. Parameterization of the design variables

In this section, the implementation of the design variables is described in detail. The research dataset for all the EnergyPlus models generated in this work is also provided to facilitate the understanding of the implementation and reproduction of the results.

PCMs. Two different models of PCMs, one for each PCM layer, are implemented and parametrized in EnergyPlus. These are implemented using the single curve model (MaterialProperty:PhaseChange), whose accuracy has been widely validated regarding experimental results and analytical solutions [41–43]. The main input required for the model is the PCM’s enthalpy curve as a function of temperature, which can be

described by up to 16 points of data. The conduction finite difference (CondFD) solution algorithm and 30 time-steps per hour are employed to guarantee accurate results, as recommended in [41].

The thicknesses of these PCMs are directly parameterized in each model. Regarding the peak melting temperatures of PCMs, the model proposed by Feustel [44] is employed to parameterize them. This model describes the enthalpy of PCMs through a hyperbolic tangent function as:

$$h(T) = c_p T + \frac{\Delta h}{2} \left\{ 1 + \tanh \left[\frac{2\beta}{\tau} (T - T_{\text{peak}}) \right] \right\}, \quad (4)$$

where c_p is the specific sensible thermal capacity in J/(kg-K), T is the temperature in °C, Δh is the specific latent heat storage capacity in J/kg, $\beta = 1.4$ is the inclination constant, τ is the temperature phase transition in °C, and T_{peak} is the peak melting temperature.

Therefore, to set the main parameters of the model in Eq. 4, the properties of Rubitherm PCMs from the RTHC line [45] are employed. Table 4 shows the properties and values used to configure Eq. 4 and the PCM model in EnergyPlus.

Table 4: Parameters were employed in the PCM modeling. Note that the density ρ and thermal conductivity k are also required to model PCMs in EnergyPlus.

Parameter	c_p [J/(kg-K)]	Δh [J/kg]	τ [°C]	β [-]	ρ [kg/m ³]	k [W/(m-K)]
Value	2000	210000	1	1.4	800	0.2

Fig. 3 shows the enthalpy curves of PCMs for the four T_{peak} levels employed in the sensitivity analysis; see Table 3.

Fig. 3: Enthalpy curves of PCMs implemented for the four T_{peak} levels using Eq. 4.

Window. The WWR is calculated as the ratio between the window’s area and the area of the wall that contains it (i.e., the south wall). The parameterization of the WWR is performed using the object Window of EnergyPlus, which allows defining the size of the window by a starting point and the height and width of the window. To implement it, a fixed window width of 7.9 m is employed, while the height is modified

according to the resulting value to comply with the WWR.

External shading. The external shading device is implemented using the object `Shading:Overhang:Projection` of EnergyPlus. Through this, a perpendicular (i.e., tilt angle regarding the window= 90°) shading is defined at the top of the window, whose width is 8 m (as the building), and its depth is parameterized as the fraction of the window height. Fig. 4 shows three combination examples for the WWR and ESR.

Fig. 4: Combination examples of the WWR and ESR. (a) WWR=50% and ESR=67% (Design 75); (b) WWR=90% and ESR=67% (Design 39); WWR=30% and ESR=100% (Design 8).

2.2.4. Calculation of the PCM effectiveness indicators

The PCM effectiveness indicators are calculated using Eq. 1. For this, the annual load saved (ALS) by the incorporation of PCMs into the building is calculated as the difference between the annual load of the Baseline model and the annual loads of its corresponding PCM model, as described in Eq. 2. Thus, to calculate the ALS for each design of the sample, the annual heating, cooling, and total loads for the PCMs models and their corresponding Baseline models are obtained as results of the EnergyPlus simulations in Osijek (Croatia).

Regarding the calculation of the latent heat storage capacity LSC installed in the building using PCMs, it is obtained as:

$$\text{LSC} = \Delta h_{\text{PCM}} * (m_{\text{PCM1}} + m_{\text{PCM2}}), \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta h_{\text{PCM}}=210000$ J/kg, and the mass of PCM layers are calculated as:

$$m_{\text{PCM1}} = \rho * \text{THK}_{\text{PCM1}} * \text{Area}_{\text{PCM1}},$$

$$m_{\text{PCM2}} = \rho * \text{THK}_{\text{PCM2}} * \text{Area}_{\text{PCM2}},$$

where $\rho = 800$ kg/m³, THK_{PCM1} and THK_{PCM2} varying according to the sample, $\text{Area}_{\text{PCM2}} = 48$ m², and $\text{Area}_{\text{PCM1}} = \text{TotalArea}_{\text{wall}} - \text{Area}_{\text{window}} = 75.6$ m² - $\text{WWR} * 0.2160$ m².

Therefore, for all the building designs in the Morris sample, the PCMEI is calculated separately for the total loads (PCMEI_{Total}), heating loads (PCMEI_{Heating}), and cooling loads (PCMEI_{Cooling}) to analyze them.

3. Results

This section describes and discusses the results obtained from the sensitivity analysis. Furthermore, the relationships between load reductions and PCMEIs are studied to better understand the behavior of the new indicators. The research dataset of this work, which includes all the EnergyPlus models and results obtained, is openly available in [46], for closer analysis (or reproduction).

3.1. Sensitivity analysis of the PCMEIs

Fig. 5 shows the sensitivity results of the Morris method, which describe the impacts of the design variables on the PCMEIs proposed. The Morris method [37] provides three main metrics: the mean of the distribution (μ), the mean of the distribution of absolute values (μ^*), and the standard deviation of the distribution (λ). The use of μ^* is recommended [47] to rank factors in order of importance because it avoids the occurrence of effects of opposite signs. Therefore, the μ^* and λ indicators for the design variables are analyzed for each PCMEI.

Fig. 5a shows the results for the PCMEI_{Heating}. It can be seen that the most influential variables for the PCM heating effectiveness (i.e., PCMEI_{Heating}) are the window-to-wall ratio (WWR) and the quantity of PCMs (i.e., THK_{PCM1} and THK_{PCM2}). In this case, the WWR controls the heat gains during the cold season, i.e., the potential extra heat to be stored in PCMs to reduce the heating loads. The installed PCM amount regulates how much extra heat can be stored in the building. The less influential variables are the melting temperatures of PCMs (i.e., $\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM1}}}$ and $\text{T}_{\text{peak}_{\text{PCM2}}}$), which is an important finding since this PCM design variable is usually thought of as the most influential one. Moreover, the influence of the wall insulation level ($\text{THK}_{\text{INSUL}}$) and external shading (ESR) is not relevant to PCMEI_{Heating}. This latter can be because of the solar altitude during the winter.

Regarding the results for the PCMEI_{Cooling}, the WWR is considerably the most influential variable, while the ERS is also highly important, followed by the PCM amount with similar relevance; see Fig. 5b.

Furthermore, the THK_{INSUL} and melting temperatures of PCMs (i.e., $T_{peak_{PCM1}}$ and $T_{peak_{PCM2}}$) are far less influential, and the THK_{INSUL} the less relevant design variable.

The results for the $PCMEI_{Total}$ are shown in Fig. 5c. Here, the WWR is again the most influential variable, followed by the THK_{PCM2} , ERS, and THK_{PCM1} . In this case, the THK_{INSUL} and melting temperatures of PCMs (i.e., $T_{peak_{PCM1}}$ and $T_{peak_{PCM2}}$) are far less influential variables. The THK_{INSUL} is also not relevant for the $PCMEI_{Total}$.

Therefore, clear and similar patterns are observed in the results between the different PCMEIs. The most relevant design variable regarding the effectiveness of PCMs is the WWR. This indicates that the high sensitivity of the WWR to control (increase or decrease) the heat gain by direct solar radiation is the key to the effectiveness of PCMs. Moreover, as shown in Fig. 5, the WWR highly influences the PCM effectiveness for all applications (i.e., the heating, cooling, and total loads).

The second most important design variable is the amount of PCMs installed in the building, which is herein characterized through the THK_{PCM2} . This is also highly relevant for PCM effectiveness for two main reasons: on the one hand, an optimal amount of PCMs is required to store and release the heat loads properly; on the other hand, an excess of PCMs can reduce their effectiveness because a substantial part of them will neither absorb nor release heat. It is worth remembering that this is properly represented by the PCMEIs proposed, since they are estimated as the ratio between the loads saved and the thermal latent capacity installed in the building using PCMs.

For similar reasons to the WWR, external shading (ERS) is also a relevant design variable for the effectiveness of PCMs. Here, the ERS is more influential for the $PCMEI_{Cooling}$ and $PCMEI_{Total}$ than the $PCMEI_{Heating}$. The remaining design variables, i.e., the PCM melting temperatures and the insulation of the walls, showed to be the less influential ones regarding the effectiveness of PCMs.

Therefore, the melting temperature of PCMs, which is usually considered one of the main variables to improve their performance, is not relevant to their effectiveness compared to other building design variables, such as the WWR and ESR, which can have a significant impact. This indicates that the effectiveness of PCMs can be greatly improved if their design is performed in the early stages, along with other building design variables. These are important and unprecedented conclusions for the field.

To further analyze the effectiveness of PCMs in buildings, Fig. 6 shows the probability distributions of the $PCMEI_{Heating}$, $PCMEI_{Cooling}$, and $PCMEI_{Total}$ obtained for the Morris sample.

Regarding the distributions for the $PCMEI_{Heating}$ and $PCMEI_{Cooling}$, these present a similar pattern, where $\simeq 70\%$ of the designs have a PCMEI between 0-5, $\simeq 20\%$ have a PCMEI between 5-10, and only a few designs have a PCMEI between 25-30. This indicates that most PCM designs have low effectiveness.

For the $PCMEI_{Total}$, the results are different in terms of magnitude because the total loads saved are higher (or at least equal) than for only one of them (heating or cooling), while the PCM capacity installed in the building is the same. Therefore, the maximum values of $PCMEI_{Total}$ are between 50 and 60. Then, $\simeq 70\%$ of the designs have a PCMEI between 0 and 10, and $\simeq 20\%$ have a PCMEI between 10 and 15.

Here, it is worth highlighting that there are no negative PCMEIs. This indicates that the incorporation of PCMs with melting temperatures within the temperature control of the ideal HVAC never worsens the

Fig. 5: Results of the mean (μ^*) and standard deviation (λ) of elementary effects for the PCMEIs. (a) PCMEI_{Heating}; (b) PCMEI_{Cooling}; (c) PCMEI_{Total}.

building's performance.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6: Probability distributions of the PCMEIs obtained for the Morris sample. (a) PCMEI_{Heating}; (b) PCMEI_{Cooling}; (c) PCMEI_{Total}.

3.2. Annual load reductions

To better understand the PCMEIs, this section analyzes the relationships between them and the annual loads. Fig. 7a shows a scatter plot between the $PCMEI_{\text{Heating}}$ and heating load reductions, where a contradicting nature between them is observed. This means that the best PCM design to reduce the heating load is not the best design to increase the effectiveness of PCMs, and vice versa. The highest heating load reduction is 68.86%, but this design has a $PCMEI_{\text{Heating}} = 3.26$. The PCM design with the highest effectiveness achieves a $PCMEI_{\text{Heating}} = 28.32$ while reducing 32.16% of the annual heating loads.

Similar behavior is observed between the $PCMEI_{\text{Cooling}}$ and cooling load reductions; see Fig. 7b. However, here the contradicting nature is stronger than between the $PCMEI_{\text{Heating}}$ and heating load reductions. The highest cooling load reduction is 73.22%, but this design has a $PCMEI_{\text{Cooling}} = 1.44$. On the other hand, the PCM design with the highest effectiveness achieves a $PCMEI_{\text{Heating}} = 27.24$ while reducing 12.75% of the annual heating loads.

Fig. 7c shows the results for the $PCMEI_{\text{Total}}$ and total load reductions. The highest total load reduction achieved is 44.37%, which is a significant amount since it is only achieved by the incorporation of PCM. However, this PCM design has a $PCMEI_{\text{Heating}} = 6.86$. On the other hand, the PCM design with the highest effectiveness achieves a $PCMEI_{\text{Total}} = 55.56$ while reducing 18.43% of the annual total loads.

The relationship between annual heating and cooling loads for all designs of the sample is shown in Fig. 7d. It can be seen that heating and cooling loads have a contradictory nature for the design variables analyzed. Furthermore, although the maximum values for the cooling loads (120 kWh/m²) are higher than the maximum for the heating loads (66 kWh/m²), some designs of the sample can have a low cooling load (≈ 3 kWh/m²), while the lowest heating loads are around 10 kWh/m².

Figs. 8a–c analyze the relationships between the PCMEI and the corresponding annual loads for heating, cooling, and total, respectively. Regarding the heating performance of PCMs, it can be seen that the design with the best $PCMEI_{\text{Heating}} = 28.32$ has an annual heating load of 33.33 kWh/m², which is similar to the mean values among the analyzed designs. On the other hand, the design with the lowest annual heating load of 9.38 kWh/m² has a $PCMEI_{\text{Heating}} = 3.26$, which indicates a quite low effectiveness of PCMs. As to the cooling performance of PCMs, it can be seen that the design with the best $PCMEI_{\text{Cooling}} = 27.24$ has an annual cooling load of 103.90 kWh/m², which is one of the worst cooling performances among the analyzed ones. On the other hand, the design with the lowest annual cooling load of 3.30 kWh/m² has a $PCMEI_{\text{Heating}} = 1.44$, which indicates a quite low effectiveness of PCMs. A similar pattern is observed between the $PCMEI_{\text{Total}}$ and annual total loads (see Fig. 8c), but with a stronger contradicting nature between them compared to the heating and cooling performances. In this case, the best $PCMEI_{\text{Total}} = 55.56$ is the design with the second highest annual total loads of 137.2 kWh/m². In the opposite scenario, the design with the lowest annual total load of 39.39 kWh/m² has a $PCMEI_{\text{Total}} = 5.03$, which indicates a low effectiveness of PCMs. Overall, a contradictory nature is observed between the PCMEIs and annual loads. This indicates that the effectiveness of PCMs is significantly higher in low-performance buildings, which is an important conclusion. The reason for this pattern is that low-performance buildings have more potential to reduce loads, and indoor temperatures present larger daily variations, improving the effectiveness of PCMs.

Fig. 7: Relationships between the PCMEIs and annual load reductions.

In practice, apart from having good PCM effectiveness, it is also needed to reduce loads. Thus, it is highly recommended to assess and optimize both the PCMEI and annual thermal loads simultaneously through a truly multi-objective approach to select the design with the best compromise. To facilitate this task, a global PCM performance indicator is proposed, which is calculated as:

$$\text{GPCMPI} = \frac{\text{PCMEI}}{\text{AL}}, \quad (6)$$

where PCMEI is the PCM effectiveness indicator obtained using Eq. 1, and the AL are the annual loads (kWh/m²) of the building with PCMs. Using this global PCM performance indicator (GPCMPI), a design with a good compromise between the PCMEI and annual loads can be obtained just by selecting the design with the maximum GPCMPI. The designs with the best GPCMPI_{Heating}, GPCMPI_{Cooling}, and GPCMPI_{Total} are indicated in Figs. 8a-c, respectively.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 8: Relationships between the PCMEIs and annual loads.

3.3. Analysis of the building designs

This section analyzes the characteristics and performance of the three specific designs obtained: the design with the best $PCMEI_{Total}$ and the design that achieves the highest total load reductions from Fig. 7c, and

the design with the best $GPCMPI_{Total}$ from Fig. 8c.

Fig. 9 summarizes the performance of the design with the best $PCMEI_{Total} = 55.56$, which is Design 198 of the sample. This design employs the lowest THK_{INSUL} (0.05 m) and ESR (1%) combined with the highest WWR (90%). Regarding the PCMs, the minimum thicknesses allowed ($THK_{PCM1} = THK_{PCM2} = 0.005$ m) are used along with a $T_{peak_{PCM1}} = 22.5$ °C and a $T_{peak_{PCM2}} = 20.5$ °C. The heat storage capacity is 96.24 MJ, which is provided by 458.3 kg of PCMs. It is worth noting that this design employs the minimum amount of PCMs possible since it combines the maximum WWR with the minimum PCM thicknesses. As shown in Fig. 8, although this design achieves high PCMEIs, it has one of the highest annual total loads (137.2 kWh/m²), which is mainly because of the cooling. The reason why this design has high PCMEIs is that the inclusion of PCMs reduces (in absolute terms) large amounts of annual heating, cooling, and total loads (i.e., 15.79 kWh/m², 15.18 kWh/m², and 30.97 kWh/m², respectively) compared to the Baseline model using a low amount of PCMs. On the other hand, the GPCMPIs indicate that the global performance of PCMs is quite good for heating but not for cooling. This demonstrates that the proposed GPCMPIs adequately analyze the contradictory nature of the PCMEIs and the annual loads.

Design 198						
I-THK [m]	WWR [%]	ESR [%]	PCM1-Tpeak [°C]	PCM2-Tpeak [°C]	PCM1-THK [m]	PCM2-THK [m]
0.0500	90	1	22.5	20.5	0.005	0.005
PCMEI [dimensionless]			GPCMPI [m ² /kWh]			PCM installed [kg]
Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total	
28.32	27.24	55.56	0.85	0.26	0.40	458.30
Annual loads			Annual relative load reductions			Storage capacity installed [MJ]
Heating [kWh/m ²]	Cooling [kWh/m ²]	Total [kWh/m ²]	Heating [%]	Cooling [%]	Total [%]	
33.30	103.91	137.20	32.16	12.75	18.42	96.24

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9: Performance summary for the design with the best $PCMEI_{Total}$ (Design 198).

Fig. 10 summarizes the performance of the design with the highest total load reductions of 44.37%, which is

Design 314 of the sample. This design uses medium values of THK_{INSUL} (0.1167 m) and ESR (67%) combined with the highest WWR (90%). Regarding the PCMs, the maximum thicknesses allowed ($THK_{PCM1} = THK_{PCM2} = 0.05$ m) are employed along with a $T_{peak_{PCM1}} = 26.5$ °C and a $T_{peak_{PCM2}} = 22.5$ °C. The heat storage capacity is 962.4 MJ, which is provided by 4583 kg of PCMs. This amount of PCMs is ten times higher than Design 198. Thus, this design shows significant reductions but has low PCMEIs and GPCMPIs due to the large amount of PCMs needed. Furthermore, it is worth noting that this design has a good balance between heating and cooling performance, and its annual total loads are 47.93 kWh/m².

Design 314						
I-THK [m]	WWR [%]	ESR [%]	PCM1-Tpeak [°C]	PCM2-Tpeak [°C]	PCM1-THK [m]	PCM2-THK [m]
0.1167	90	67	26.5	22.5	0.05	0.05
PCMEI [dimensionless]			GPCMPI [m ² /kWh]			PCM installed [kg]
Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total	
3.19	3.67	6.86	0.13	0.16	0.14	4583
Annual loads			Annual relative load reductions			Storage capacity installed [MJ]
Heating [kWh/m ²]	Cooling [kWh/m ²]	Total [kWh/m ²]	Heating [%]	Cooling [%]	Total [%]	
24.40	23.52	47.93	42.13	46.50	44.37	962.44

(a)

(b)

Fig. 10: Performance summary for the design with the highest total load reduction (Design 314).

Fig. 11 shows the performance of the design with the highest $GPCMPI_{Total} = 0.52$, which is Design 286 of the sample. This design uses medium values of THK_{INSUL} (0.0833 m) and ESR (67%) combined with the highest WWR (90%). Regarding the PCMs, the minimum thicknesses allowed ($THK_{PCM1} = THK_{PCM2} = 0.005$ m) are employed along with melting temperatures $T_{peak_{PCM1}} = T_{peak_{PCM2}} = 22.5$ °C. The heat storage capacity is 96.24 MJ, which is provided by 458.3 kg of PCMs. This design also has a good balance between heating and cooling performances, and its annual total loads are 69.89 kWh/m². Therefore, the design with the highest GPCMPI (Design 286) achieves very competitive load reductions compared to Design 135 but employs ten times less amount of PCMs, which indicates a high PCM effectiveness and

confirms the usefulness of the GPCMPIs proposed.

Design 286						
I-THK [m]	WWR [%]	ESR [%]	PCM1-Tpeak [°C]	PCM2-Tpeak [°C]	PCM1-THK [m]	PCM2-THK [m]
0.0833	90	67	22.5	22.5	0.005	0.005
PCMEI [dimensionless]			GPCMPI [m ² /kWh]			PCM installed [kg]
Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total	
21.00	15.35	36.36	0.58	0.46	0.52	458.30
Annual loads			Annual relative load reductions			Storage capacity installed [MJ]
Heating [kWh/m ²]	Cooling [kWh/m ²]	Total [kWh/m ²]	Heating [%]	Cooling [%]	Total [%]	
36.15	33.74	69.89	24.47	20.23	22.48	96.24

Fig. 11: Performance summary for the design with the best GPCMPI_{Total} (Design 286).

4. Conclusions

Novel indicators were introduced to quantify the effectiveness of passive phase change materials (PCMs) in buildings. These indicators aim to overcome the limitations of the current state-of-the-art by calculating the effectiveness of PCMs as the ratio between the annual load reductions (i.e., the heating, cooling, or total loads) achieved through PCM utilization and the installed heat latent storage capacity in the building.

To assess the influence of both PCM and building design variables on the PCM effectiveness indicators, a sensitivity analysis was conducted using the Morris method. A case study building located in Zone 4A (Mixed), according to the ASHRAE 169-2021 climate classification, was employed for this purpose. Building performance simulations were performed using EnergyPlus for each design. The design variables considered in this analysis were the melting temperatures (T_{peak_PCM1} and T_{peak_PCM2}) and thicknesses (THK_{PCM1} and THK_{PCM2}) of two different PCM layers located in the ceiling and external walls. Additionally, the impact of the insulation thickness (THK_{INSUL}) of the walls, the window-to-wall ratio (WWR), and the external shading

length normalized as the ratio to the window height (ESR) were also evaluated as design variables related to the building envelope.

Important findings and conclusions can be drawn from all the achieved results. The sensitivity analysis revealed that the WWR, PCM amount (THK_{PCM1} and THK_{PCM2}), and ESR are the most significant design variables impacting the effectiveness of PCMs. Surprisingly, the melting temperatures and the insulation level of external walls were found to have a lesser influence on the effectiveness of PCMs in buildings. This finding is unprecedented, as historically, the melting temperature was considered the primary PCM design parameter. These findings suggest that the effectiveness of PCMs can be significantly improved by integrating their design with other building design variables, preferably during the initial stages.

To acquire a deeper understanding of the new PCM effectiveness indicators (PCMEIs), further analyses were conducted on the distributions of PCMEIs and the relationships between the magnitudes of PCMEIs and annual thermal loads. From these results, an initial observation was made: the values of PCMEIs are predominantly low compared to the theoretical maximum of 365. The maximum PCMEI values obtained for both the heating and cooling loads were between 25 and 30. Regarding the PCMEI for the total loads, the maximum values were between 50 and 60. Moreover, the results showed that important maximum relative savings can be achieved by PCM utilization regarding the heating loads (69%), cooling loads (73%), and total loads (44%).

Regarding the relationships between the magnitudes of PCMEIs and annual thermal loads, it was found that a contradictory nature exists between PCMEIs and annual load reductions as well as between PCMEIs and annual loads. This indicates two important conclusions. The first one is that the effectiveness of PCMs is significantly higher in low-performance buildings. This is because these buildings have more potential to reduce loads, and their indoor temperatures present larger daily variations, improving the effectiveness of PCMs. The second is that the design of PCMs in high-performance buildings should be performed along with other design variables to improve their effectiveness, preferably at early stages. To achieve this, a truly multi-objective approach is recommended because of the contradictory nature of PCMEIs and annual load reductions. Otherwise, a global PCM performance indicator was proposed and validated in this work as the ratio between the PCMEIs and the annual loads.

The redefinition of the effectiveness of PCMs achieved in this work allowed for important findings to understand the physical behavior of passive PCMs in buildings and new areas of research to improve their effectiveness. In this sense, several aspects not included in this work will be addressed in future research.

Based on the obtained findings, it is suggested to research the best trade-off between PCM effectiveness and annual building thermal loads. This should be performed for various building typologies and climate regions to obtain comprehensive conclusions. Furthermore, other building and PCM design variables should be included, as well as other passive strategies (e.g., natural ventilation). Another important research goal is to generalize the PCM effectiveness indicators to address other operative modes (e.g., free-running buildings) and active applications of PCMs in buildings.

Data availability

The research data achieved in this work, including all the results and EnergyPlus models, can be found at <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8081729> for closer analysis (or reproduction).

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